

Terrain Slope and Surface Roughness Studies using Circularly Polarized SAR Backscatter

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Abstract - In this paper we use a new SAR technique for measurement of terrain slopes in the azimuthal (along-track) direction for correction of terrain slope-related polarimetric effects in SAR surface roughness, or soil moisture, inversion studies. A second goal is determination of the sensitivity of a circular polarization correlation function for the measurement of terrain slopes and surface roughness.

INTRODUCTION

Recent polarimetric SAR studies of surface roughness [1] indicate that more sensitive measurements may be made using circular polarizations. Surface roughness is difficult to characterize even for flat-earth conditions because of variability in the surface autocorrelation function, rms height, and the dielectric constant. A further factor complicating such studies, for terrain having significant relief, are the effects of larger-scale terrain slopes. Terrain slopes in both the range- and azimuthal-directions can result in significant changes in the received polarimetric SAR scatter matrix values and, thus, also contaminate the SAR-derived surface roughness measurements. A new method is available [2] to measure terrain slopes in the azimuthal direction using polarimetric SAR data. For cases where data is available in two orthogonal directions, a complete terrain elevation surface may be developed and slope measurements may be made for any direction.

The purpose of this paper is to show that 1) the polarimetric effects of terrain slopes on the complex covariance matrix [C] are correctable, and 2) the circular-pol RR and LL correlation coefficient, ρ_{RRLL} , is a sensitive measure of the combined effects of sub-resolution cell surface roughness and rms slope. The results reported here are for an area of desert, open-terrain near Stovepipe Wells in Death Valley, CA. The data used is NASA/JPL/AIRSAR P-, L-, and C-band calibrated, fully polarimetric SAR data obtained in October, 1994. The Death Valley data was chosen because the largely open-terrain could be modelled as a grid of tilted-slab SAR resolution cells (6.6m by 8.25m) which contain sub-resolution slopes and small-scale roughness.

The methods developed in [1-2] provide a means, using polarimetric SAR data, of combining sensitive surface roughness measurements with terrain azimuthal slope measurements. Investigations have been made using the complex circular-pol covariance matrix [C] whose terms are $\langle S_{ij}S_{kl}^* \rangle$, where i,j,k,l are right-hand or left-hand polarizations of the received SAR signals. The diagonal elements of [C] are real and rotationally-invariant about the line of sight.

Azimuthal slopes, with spatial extent larger than the resolution cell, rotate the polarimetric orientation of scatter from the cell. In another study, the polarimetric orientation rotation δ (measured in a plane perpendicular to the look-direction) may be related to the actual azimuthal terrain slope, $\tan(\beta)$ by

$$\tan \delta = \frac{-\tan \beta}{\sin \theta + \cos \theta \tan \gamma} \quad (1)$$

where, θ is the look-direction and $\tan(\gamma)$ is the surface slope in the ground-range direction. The look-angle θ is known from the flight data collection geometry. The angle γ is not known except when an accurate Digital Elevation Model (DEM) is available. The effect of γ in determining terrain slopes diminishes as $\theta \Rightarrow 90^\circ$. In this paper only terrain-induced changes in the polarimetric orientation angle δ are measured and corrected.

An image for the open-terrain study-site is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: A C-band(span) image of the Death Valley, CA. site.

The rugged slopes visible on the image left are the Kit Fox Hills which rise to 300m above the valley floor. The desert

basin in the center of the image contains well-studied (Sir-C Super-Site) alluvial fans and (dark-patch) eroded wash areas. The bright localized spots on the upper-left are short trees and bushes growing on an area of large sand-dunes.

CIRCULAR-POL MEASUREMENTS OF SLOPES AND AND SURFACE ROUGHNESS

All of the circular-pol results reported here are derived from AIRSAR measurements of the complex linear-pol scattering matrix [S]. Conversion relations between linear and circular bases are well-known. Of interest here is the circular-pol covariance matrix for scattering from a single scatter-cell polarimetrically rotated by an angle δ in the azimuthal

$$[C] = \begin{bmatrix} S_{LL}S_{LL}^* & S_{LL}S_{LR}^*e^{-j2\delta} & S_{LL}S_{RR}^*e^{-j4\delta} \\ S_{LR}S_{LL}^*e^{j2\delta} & S_{LR}S_{LR}^* & S_{LR}S_{RR}^*e^{-j2\delta} \\ S_{RR}S_{LL}^*e^{j4\delta} & S_{RR}S_{LR}^*e^{j2\delta} & S_{RR}S_{RR}^* \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

direction. This matrix is given in Equation (2).

The off-diagonal term $S_{RR}S_{LL}^*e^{j4\delta}$ has been averaged and converted into a complex correlation coefficient ρ_{RRL} as

$$\rho_{RRL} = \frac{\langle S_{RR}S_{LL}^*e^{j4\delta} \rangle}{\sqrt{\langle |S_{RR}|^2 \rangle \langle |S_{LL}|^2 \rangle}} \quad (3)$$

where, an ensemble average of backscatter and tilt-effects has been taken over a [5x5] grid surrounding each matrix location. The real part of Eqn. (3) represents that portion of the scatter which is azimuthally symmetric. The axis of symmetry of the scatter has been rotated by some δ , for each of the averaged cells, in an orientation-plane perpendicular to the look-direction vector. It is apparent that reduction of the value of ρ_{RRL} comes from both scatter-cell orientation tilts δ and from the effects of unresolved slopes and surface roughness within the cell. The relatively simple case of a tilted cell containing only small-scale roughness (i.e., sloping, plowed fields) is only decorrelated by the single-slope and by the rms roughness. The Death Valley study-area, however, contains more complex terrain with terrain slopes having a wide range of scales.

Fig. 2(a-b) shows grey-scale images of $\text{Re}[\rho_{RRL}]$ values from black($\rho=0$) to white($\rho=1$). The blackened areas of Fig 2(a) near the slopes of the Kit Fox Hills which arise out of the valley are likely to be decorrelated by predominately azimuthal direction slope-effects rather than by large changes in surface roughness. Fig. 2(b) has been corrected for these slope effects by multiplying each pixel value by the complex-conjugate of $\exp(j4\delta)$ estimated from the real/imaginary parts of ρ_{RRL} . It should be noted that these new type of δ estimates are highly correlated with estimates produced with the more-established polarization signature method of [2].

Fig. 2: a) Values of $\text{Re}[\rho_{RRL}]$ for the study area, and b): values for $\text{Re}[\rho_{RRL}]$ corrected for azimuthal slope effects.

Notice that the large-scale slope-effects have been largely eliminated from the scene. A comparison (Fig.3) for a profile transecting Death Valley has been made of ρ_{RRL} (solid-line) and the linear-pol ρ_{HHVV} (dashed-line) correlation coefficients, which were both investigated in [1]. A low value of ρ , for the same surface roughness, indicates better sensitivity. The dip at 4 km is the desert-basin wash area in the center of the image which is detected by ρ_{RRL} but largely missed by ρ_{HHVV} .

Fig. 3: Comparison of the sensitivity of ρ_{RRL} and ρ_{HHVV} to slopes and variation in surface roughness.

CORRECTION OF STOKES MATRIX VALUES FOR TERRAIN AZIMUTHAL SLOPE EFFECTS

The results correcting ρ_{RRL} provided the drive to attempt to polarimetrically compensate, or "flatten", a scene and eliminate the rotationally symmetric effects of azimuthal tilts.

In this effort the slopes were compensated by estimates of scatter-cell tilt provided by the shift in the position of the maximum in the polarimetric signature surface plot [2]. The polarimetric orientation changes δ caused by Death Valley

azimuthal slopes are shown in Fig. 4(a) for P-band data. The same surface after compensation for these slopes, shown in Fig.4(b), is almost completely flattened. Similar results were obtained when the slope compensation algorithm was applied to L-band data for the same scene.

Fig. 4: a) Polarimetric orientation angles, δ , caused by terrain slopes for the entire study-area, and b) the same data corrected for slope-effects.

A plot is shown in Fig. 5 which transects the study-site. The reduction in the slope-induced orientation angles δ is quite good. Examination of HH,VV,and HV total power images after compensation appear normal except for removal of slope detail in both the desert-basin and in Kit Fox Hills.

Fig. 5: Profile of orientation change δ values for a transect across Death valley and the Kit Fox Hills. The solid line is before slope correction; the dashed line is after correction.

As an indication that the desired flat-earth data has not been contaminated by the correction procedure, Fig.6(a-b) shows conventional polarimetric signatures before and after slope corrections.

Fig. 6: Polarimetric signature ($\chi=0$) profiles from a [6x6] cell average for an area in the Kit Fox Hills a) with no slope-corrections (orientation max=70°) and, b) with slope-corrections (orientation max=90°). The signature in (b) is consistent with a flat-earth Bragg (single bounce) scatter signature.

The terrain slope estimation method has corrected the effects that a large azimuthal slope had on the polarimetric signature. The residual signature of Fig.6(b) is consistent with a flat-earth Bragg (single-bounce) scatter polarimetric signature.

CONCLUSIONS

A technique has been proposed and tested for the polarimetric correction of terrain azimuthal slope effects on SAR backscatter data. The intent is that the method will be useful for future surface roughness and soil moisture studies in areas where the terrain has significant relief.

The new technique does not require the use of an externally provided Digital Elevation Model (DEM) which is often not available. Secondly, the circular-pol correlation coefficient ρ_{RLL} appears to be more sensitive than ρ_{HHVV} as a combined measure of terrain slopes and surface roughness. Analysis using data-sets with better surface roughness ground truth in sloping terrain is required to prove the usefulness of ρ_{RLL} .

REFERENCES

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